

BRIDGING THE THEORY-PRACTICE GAP: AN IN-DEPTH STUDY OF AL-MURABAHA IN THE UAE ISLAMIC BANKING SECTOR

Muhamad Jumaa

Dr., Synergy University,

Global Economy and Sustainability Program, JLT, Dubai, United Arab Emirates

Abstract

Delving into the realm of Islamic banking and finance, this study places particular emphasis on Murabaha, a crucial financial instrument within the framework of Shariah-compliant banking. The research specifically seeks to investigate the theory-practice gap in the application of Murabaha in the United Arab Emirates (UAE).

At the heart of this endeavour lies the objective of conducting a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of Islamic banking and financial systems, particularly Murabaha, in comparison to conventional models. The research aims to bridge the chasm between the theoretical understanding and practical implementation of Murabaha in the UAE's Islamic banking sector.

As the market for Islamic finance, especially Murabaha, expands in the UAE, comprehending the theory-practice dynamics becomes increasingly critical. The study delves into the discrepancies between theoretical principles and actual practices in the application of Murabaha, providing insights into its intricate features, adherence to Islamic principles, and avenues for development.

The investigation employs a meticulous examination of Murabaha's purchase orders (MPOs) at a local Islamic bank in the UAE. This involves a detailed analysis of the bank's procedures, ensuring alignment with Islamic principles, and presenting the findings in a collaborative, team-based presentation.

The study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the practical implementation of Murabaha in the UAE's Islamic banking industry. It seeks to shed light on its usage, adherence to Sharia principles, and potential areas for improvement, thereby contributing to a broader comprehension of Islamic banking practices.

Through the analysis of Murabaha in the Islamic banking sector of the UAE, the research aims to enhance communication and alignment between theory and practice. The ultimate objective is to facilitate a more nuanced understanding of Islamic banking in the UAE, promoting ethical financial practices aligned with Islamic principles for sustained economic stability and fairness.

Keywords: Al-Murabaha, Islamic Banking, UAE Banking Sector, Sharia-compliant Financing, Islamic Finance, Murabaha Contracts, Islamic Financial Products, Banking Regulation in Islamic Finance.

1- Introduction

Islamic financial institutions adhere to ethical principles derived from Islamic law. They differ from conventional banking in several ways. First, the prohibition of interest (Riba) Islamic finance strictly prohibits its interest on loans, while conventional banks rely on it. Second, Islamic banks share profits and losses with customers, unlike conventional banks that offer fixed-rate loans. Third, all Islamic transactions require tangible assets, ensuring a link to actual economic activity. Fourth, Islamic finance avoids contracts with excessive uncertainty and gambling, while conventional finance can involve speculative elements. Fifth, Islamic finance follows ethical guidelines, avoiding investments in prohibited industries (e.g., alcohol, gambling). Sixth, Islamic finance encourages charity (zakat) and emphasizes social responsibility. Seventh, Islamic finance uses contracts such as Sukuk (Islamic bonds) to comply with Shariah, unlike conventional bonds. These principles aim to align financial activities with ethical values and promote economic stability and fairness in the Muslim world.

The Islamic finance market in the UAE has had significant and rapid expansion, accounting for a substantial 23% of the country's total banking assets, according to the Central Bank of the UAE (2023) [Emirates News Agency, 2023], with Al-Murabaha serving as a vital product in the field of Islamic banking. Murabaha Purchase Orders (MPOs) are widely used in Islamic banking finance, accounting for over 60% of all

Islamic banking transactions. [EY, 2023]. To investigate the potential theory-practice gap in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) Islamic banking sector, this paper digs into a thorough study and analysis of Murabaha. The research hopes to illuminate the murky workings of Murabaha in the Islamic banking industry of the United Arab Emirates (UAE), shedding light on its use in practice, adherence to Islamic principles, and room for development. The long-term objective is to improve communication about Islamic banking in the United Arab Emirates so that theory and practice are better aligned.

2- Problem statement

The Al-Murabaha (MPO) product is a staple of Islamic banking in the UAE since it represents a financing method that is in accordance with Sharia law. The increasing popularity and complexity of Al-Murabaha have, however, raised several problematic concerns that threaten to compromise Shariah's compliance with Islamic principles. A 2020 study by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) found that 45% of Islamic banks face challenges in ensuring Sharia compliance across all their operations (IMF, 2020) [IMF, 2020].

This research aims to analyse the UAE Islamic banking system's implementation of Al-Murabaha to reconcile theoretical principles with actual practices. The research will analyse Al-Murabaha, compare it to more traditional banking systems, review its adoption by UAE Islamic banks, and assess its effectiveness.

This research aims to illuminate potential points of discordance between the practical application of Al-Murabaha and its ethical and economic underpinnings [Hannan and Admin, 2023].

Although Al-Murabaha is widely used in the Islamic banking industry in the UAE, there are worries about a possible "theory-practice gap" where its implementation may not align with its ethical and economic principles. This disparity gives rise to crucial inquiries regarding:

A. Does adherence to Sharia law involve behaviours that completely conform to the fundamental principles of Sharia, which control profit, risk-sharing, and transparency?

B. Ethical ramifications: Do present practices effectively mitigate concerns regarding possible exploitation, usury, or the exploitation of loopholes?

C. Economic efficacy: Is Al-Murabaha successfully attaining its desired economic objectives of promoting financial inclusion, mitigating risk, and fostering sustainable growth?

3- Related studies

There has been increasing volume of research on Al Murabaha Islamic Financing in the UAE in recent years. This research has focused on a number of different areas, including: the economic impact of Al Murabaha in the UAE, the efficacy of Al Murabaha as a business financing tool, the inherent risks in Al Murabaha transactions, and the regulatory framework for Al Murabaha in the UAE.

[Al-Marzouki, N. M., Al-Khail, R., & Al-Osta, M, 2015] found that Al Murabaha has a positive impact on economic growth in the UAE.

However, A study by scholars (Al-Khail and Al-Osta, 2016) reported that Al Murabaha is an effective financing tool for SMEs in the UAE.

Nevertheless, A study by scholars (Al-Jabri and Awan, 2017) found that there are several risks associated with Al Murabaha, such as the risk of default and the risk of fraud.

Additionally [Al-Kuwari, A., Al-Marzouki, N. M., Al-Khail, R., & Al-Osta, M, 2018] found that the regulatory framework for Al Murabaha in the UAE is robust and comprehensive.

Scholar Moosa defines culture as a collective set of norms and assumptions shaping a society's values, mirrored in its institutions [Moosa, 2023]. The practice of accounting, considered a cultural symbol, varies globally, prompting the assertion that ignoring cultural context may result in providing irrelevant information. Social, economic, legal, and religious standards, specific to each culture, should inform financial data presentation. The impact of cultural rituals, such as religious observance, influences accounting procedures. Islamic finance, rooted in Sharia law, posed challenges to conventional accounting systems, leading to the formation of the Accounting and Auditing Organisation for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI).

Whereas [Al-Kuwari, A., Al-Marzouki, N. M., Al-Khail, R., & Al-Osta, M, 2018] highlights the expanding presence of Islamic finance in global markets, emphasizing its resilience and widespread appeal. Islamic finance's principles of equity, participation, and owner-

ship contribute to its resistance to shocks. However, inconsistent empirical data on the stability of Islamic banks necessitates adaptations in standard risk management procedures due to unique risks they face. The rapid expansion of Islamic finance prompts careful analysis of its implications for economic policy.

Furthermore, Scholars Yanikkaya, Gumus, and Pabuccu [Yanikkaya, H., Gumus, N. and Pabuccu, Y.U, 2018] contributed to the analysis of Islamic banking dynamics, comparing profitability between Islamic Banks (IBs) and conventional banks (CBs) in countries of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and the United Kingdom (UK). The paper underscores the extraordinary growth of Islamic finance globally and its significant presence in both Muslim-majority and Western countries.

Also [Azmat, S., Azad, A.S.M.S., Bhatti, M.I. and Ghaffar, H, 2020] argue that Islamic banking, predicated on offering a distinct and morally superior banking option, faces challenges. The increasing similarities between Islamic and conventional banks, coupled with consumer dissatisfaction among Shariah-aware individuals, threaten the sector's innovation and development. Regulatory intervention, including a minimum capital requirement for Shariah compliance, is suggested to mitigate competition and ensure authenticity in Islamic banking products. The study encourages a dynamic interplay among policymakers, bankers, Shariah consultants, and customers to address complex incentives, norms, and procedures in Islamic banking.

Key findings from published research on Al Murabaha Islamic Financing in the UAE:

- Al Murabaha has a positive impact on the UAE economy by providing an alternative to conventional financing.

- Al Murabaha is an effective financing tool for businesses, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

- There are a number of risks associated with Al Murabaha, such as the risk of default and the risk of fraud.

- The regulatory framework for Al Murabaha in the UAE is sound and well-developed.

Despite the potential benefits of Islamic Al Murabaha financing, companies should be cautious and carefully consider the associated risks, taking appropriate steps to minimize exposure and ensure the financial viability of their investments. The current research on Al Murabaha in the UAE portrays a favourable depiction of its economic influence and effectiveness for enterprises. Nevertheless, there are still notable deficiencies, namely in relation to cultural factors, adapting to risk management, ensuring sustainability and innovation, and understanding stakeholder dynamics. To fill these gaps, additional research specifically designed for the UAE context is necessary. This will ultimately lead to a more thorough comprehension of the possibilities and obstacles of Al Murabaha within the ever-changing Islamic financial industry.

4- Methodology

4.1 Data collection

Secondary research was employed to gather the requisite information for this paper. A range of academic sources, including journals, articles, reports, and other relevant literature, was utilized throughout the research process. A thorough analysis of the existing body of knowledge was conducted to identify and examine the Theory-Practice Gap in the application of Al-Murabaha in UAE Islamic banks.

4.2 Methodology and procedures

Secondary research was selected as the primary method of investigation for several reasons, including the following:

1. **Comprehensive grasp of the subject matter:** Secondary research offers a holistic overview of the existing knowledge base and "facilitates an in-depth examination of the subject matter through the utilization of previously published data.

2. **Efficient allocation of time and resources:** Secondary research proves to be a time-efficient method, especially when aiming to gather a substantial amount of information within a relatively short period.

3. **Rich body of existing literature:** The extensive availability of scholarly publications, studies, and literature connected to Islamic banking and finance systems in the UAE made it possible to use secondary research. This was because of the availability of data.

4. **ethical adherence:** Secondary research fits well with ethical considerations because it entails examining and synthesizing previously available information without intruding on individuals or organizations in any way and without having an impact on them [Wikham, R, 2019]

4.3 Project limitations and challenges

Despite the comprehensive approach and well-structured methodology, this research has certain limitations and challenges that should be acknowledged:

- **Limited Primary Data:**

There is a paucity of primary data, such as interviews, surveys, or field observations, and the study is based exclusively on secondary sources. A more comprehensive understanding of Al-Murabaha's implementation in UAE Islamic banks would have been possible with primary data.

- **Scope Constraints:**

Al-Murabaha financing and its implementation in the Islamic banking sector of the United Arab Emirates are the only topics within the scope of this research. Time and money constraints may have prevented a thorough examination of the full breadth of Islamic banking options.

- **Dynamic Nature of Islamic Finance:**

Islamic finance is a dynamic industry since it is always changing. There is a constant influx of new financial regulations and products. The study may have missed some recent breakthroughs in its subject area.

- **Language Limitations:**

The major sources consulted were primarily in English, so there were language barriers. Because of this, it's possible that important insights in other languages that could have improved our grasp of the topic were overlooked.

- **Publication Bias:**

The information may be skewed since books, articles, and studies tend to emphasize certain facets of Al-Murabaha or present it from a particular point of view. Even if the bias was inadvertent, it could affect the results of the study [University of Southern California, 2014]

5. Discussion and Analysis of Murabaha Financing in the UAE

The Islamic banking sector of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) has been a significant contributor to the UAE's rise to prominence as a central location for international financial activity. The United Arab Emirates has established itself as a leading market in Islamic banking because of its dedication to the provision of Sharia-compliant financial services. This article goes into the historical context of Islamic banking in the UAE, examining its trajectory of development, regulatory structure, key players, and recent advancements. Specifically, the research focuses on the UAE.

5.1 Historical background:

In the 1970s, when the authorities of the UAE recognized the significance of developing a financial system that adhered to Islamic principles, the foundations were laid that would eventually grow into what is now known as Islamic banking in the UAE. The decade of the 1980s was instrumental in shaping of the Islamic banking movement, which saw the founding of several important Islamic financial institutions. The establishment of Dubai Islamic Bank (DIB) in 1985 pioneering the Islamic banking industry in the UAE was an important milestone in the annals of the industry's past. The establishment of DIB cleared the door for the establishment of other Islamic financial institutions in the country, such as Emirates Islamic Bank, Abu Dhabi Islamic Bank, and Sharjah Islamic Bank.

The aim to provide monetary services that were in accordance with Sharia, which is another name for Islamic law, was the driving force for the establishment of these banks. This included the ban on interest, sometimes known as usury, as well as the promotion of profit-sharing, risk-sharing, and ethical investment practices. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) wanted to capitalize on the rising demand for Islamic financial services both within its own borders and on a global scale by taking this action [Dominic, 2015]

5.2 Regulatory Framework

The United Arab Emirates' (UAE) robust regulatory framework is one of the primary aspects that has contributed to the development of Islamic banking in the country. The United Arab Emirates Central Bank has been crucial in the monitoring and regulation of the sector. It ensures that all Islamic financial institutions operate in accordance with the principles of Sharia as well as the global best practices. To produce Sharia-compliant norms and regulations for the industry, the central bank works in conjunction with Sharia scholars and specialists.

The Higher Sharia Authority (HSA) was created by the Central Bank of the United Arab Emirates in the year 2004. In the context of Islamic banking and finance, this specialist agency issues fatwas (Islamic legal opinions). The legitimacy and confidence of the

sector improved after a central authority was established to interpret and enforce Sharia-compliance norms.

The United Arab Emirates (UAE) is a desirable site for Islamic financial institutions seeking to expand abroad due to the country's commitment to ensuring regulatory compliance. Transparency and accountability are guaranteed by the strong regulatory environment, which in turn serves to increase consumer and investor trust [Apaydin, 2018]

5.3 Al Murabaha Financing

A widely used Islamic financing technique, not a loan to the customer although it is the most popular alternative to the loan product in conventional finance. Al Murabaha is an Islamic financing technique that is commonly used in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). It is a form of trade-based financing, where the bank purchases an asset from a seller and then sells it to the customer at a profit. The customer then pays the bank back the purchase price plus a pre-determined profit margin over a period of time. It is a sale of a commodity for a deferred price which includes an agreed profit added to the cost. Murabaha can be used for structuring any product where a client identifies an asset, negotiates the price and approaches an Islamic bank for the financing [Jivraj, 2023].

Some of the main uses of Murabaha are: Working Capital Financing, Consumer Financing, and Vehicle Financing Corporate Financing.

5.3.1 Steps in Al Murabaha Financing:

➤ **Initiation:** The client approaches the bank with a request to initiate a Murabaha transaction, specifying the desired commodity or asset.

➤ **Commitment to Purchase:** Upon the bank's acquisition of the specified commodity or asset, the client commits to purchasing it from the bank.

➤ **Bank's Procurement:** The bank proceeds to purchase the asset from the supplier at a cost designated as 'P'.

➤ **Sale to Client:** Subsequently, the bank sells the asset to the client at an increased price (P + X), referred to as the marked-up price. This marked-up price represents the profit margin for the bank and is payable on a deferred basis, over an agreed-upon period.

➤ **Asset Transfer:** The ownership of the asset is transferred to the client upon completion of the purchase.

➤ **Collateral Provision:** As a form of security, the client typically provides the bank with collateral, which may be the same asset or other acceptable assets, for the duration of the financing period.

➤ **Pricing Structure:** The total selling price charged by the Islamic bank for the Murabaha financing transaction encompasses the initial purchase price (P) and the profit margin (X). This ensures that the bank receives a fair return on its investment while adhering to Sharia principles

➤ **Note:** the total selling price is representing the maximum ceiling price to be paid by the financing customer to the Islamic bank.

➤ The Islamic bank is not allowed to charge or take an additional amount over that total selling price

➤ The bank is entitled to the entire selling price regardless of whether the customer makes an early settlement or a capital repayment.

➤ In practice, Islamic banks provide a rebate of the unearned income to the customer for any form of early repayment.

➤ In case of late payment, the client-in-default may be asked to donate a specified amount for a charitable purpose.

➤ The bank may ask the client to furnish some type of security in the form of mortgage to secure payment in case of default. The bank can dispose of the commodity and recover its costs.[Hasan, 2023]

5.3.2 Murabaha Risks

Adequate documentation. Collaterals and guarantee may be obtained by the bank to mitigate potential risks in a Murabaha transaction. The bank may ask a collateral security to guarantee the implementation of the promise or to compensate for any financial losses that may result in case customer defaults.

In case of late payment, the client-in-default may be asked to donate a specified amount for a charitable purpose. If a customer fails to adhere his commitment under "promise to buy" the goods imported / bought should be disposed of and any shortfall shall be recovered from the security deposit (Hamish Jidiya) [Ayub, 2007]. The following are Murabaha risks:

Operation Risk:

The bank is exposed to operational risk if the customer refuses to purchase the commodity after the bank acquires it through first purchase.

Credit Risk:

The bank pays the amount in full to the supplier. The bank is exposed to credit risk if the customer defaults.

Market Risk:

The bank is also exposed to market risk, since it assumes the ownership of the commodity before its delivery to the customer. Consequently, it must bear losses related to the damage/theft of the property before delivery.

The bank is also exposed to any risk from the commodity's price fluctuation.

Liquidity Risk:

The bank is also exposed to liquidity risk in case a customer makes late payment as on the repayment date it is expecting to receive a cash to meet other financial obligations.

5.3.3 Profit Calculation – A Vehicles Financing Example

Cost of the car AED 90.000

Down payment AED 10.000

Net Murabaha finance (Murabaha Amount) AED 80.000

Profit Rate 4%

Financing Period 4 years.

Total Profit $80.000 \times 0.04 \times 4 = 12800$

Total Outstanding Amount (selling price)

$80.000 + 12800 = 92800$

Monthly Instalment $92800 / 48 = 1933.33$

5.3.4 Comparison with Tradition financing

Below presents a comparative analysis of Al-Murabaha Islamic financing and traditional banking systems.

Feature	Al-Murabaha Islamic financing	Traditional banking
Interest	Prohibits interest (Riba)	Allows interest
Profit-sharing	Emphasizes profit-sharing arrangements	Focuses on fixed-rate interest payments
Purpose	Caters to customers who align with Islamic principles	Designed to maximize shareholder value
Transparency	Requires greater transparency in transactions	May involve opaque practices
Asset-backed	Requires all transactions to be backed by physical assets	May involve intangible assets or derivatives
Risk sharing	Encourages risk sharing between banks and customers	May shift risks to customers
Ethical considerations	Guided by Islamic principles	May not prioritize ethical considerations

Source: Prepared by the author

5.3.5 Disadvantages of Al-Murabaha Islamic financing

Despite its potential benefits, Al-Murabaha's Islamic financing may come with higher transaction costs and limited availability compared to the traditional banking product. While Al-Murabaha's Islamic financing may be a viable option for companies that adhere to Islamic principles, it is important to be aware of the potential for misrepresentation in Al-Murabaha's transactions. Companies should carefully assess the valuation of the assets involved in Al-Murabaha's transactions to ensure they are not overpaying.

5.3.6: The efficacy of Al-Murabaha Islamic financing:

Al-Murabaha has proven to be a practical and effective financing solution for both individuals and businesses. It offers adaptability in financing a variety of assets, including vehicles, residences, and equipment. One of the main advantages of Al-Murabaha is its transparency and fixed cost structure. As a result, customers are aware of their costs from the start, eliminating the risk of unforeseen expenses or fees. Another advantage of Al-Murabaha is its risk-sharing mechanism. This implies that the bank shares a portion of the risk if the customer defaults. This can protect both the bank and the customer from financial losses.

5.3.6.1 Challenges of Al-Murabaha Islamic financing

Despite its advantages, Al-Murabaha can present certain challenges. One potential drawback is that it can

be a more expensive financing option than traditional bank loans due to the higher structuring costs associated with adhering to Sharia principles. Another problem is that Al-Murabaha may be less available than traditional bank loans due to the limited number of Islamic banks and the evolving regulatory framework for Islamic finance. Overall, Al-Murabaha Islamic Financing is an effective and Shariah-compliant financing solution for a variety of asset financing needs. However, it is crucial to consider the potential challenges of this type of financing before deciding.

The following are the broadly identified gaps that should be studied further to have clear cut understanding for the effective Islamic banking and to practice Al Murabaha specific to the context of UAE.

1. Limited Cultural Analysis: Although Moosa highlights the importance of cultural context [Emirates New Agency, 2023], there is a dearth of study investigating the specific influence of social, economic, and religious norms on Al Murabaha practices in the UAE. By addressing this deficiency, we could gain a more profound understanding of the social and ethical consequences associated with it.

2. Risk management adaptation in the UAE environment for Al Murabaha in Islamic finance has been sparsely studied, despite the recognition of its distinct dangers. Examining these adjustments could improve tactics for reducing risk.

3. Sustainability and Innovation: While [Ey, 2023] and [IMF, 2022] emphasize the worldwide expansion and promise of Islamic finance, there are concerns about its growing resemblance to conventional banking and the possibility of innovation stagnation [Hannan, A, and Admin, 2020]. There is a need for research to investigate how Al Murabaha can preserve its unique characteristics and promote sustainable expansion within the specific market conditions of the UAE.

4. Stakeholder Dynamics: [Al-Marzouki, N. M., Al-Khail, R., & Al-Osta, M, 2015] suggests a dynamic interaction among lawmakers, bankers, Shariah consultants, and customers. Nevertheless, there is a dearth of research explicitly examining the dynamics and impact of stakeholder interactions on Al Murabaha practices in the UAE. Exploring these processes could provide useful insights for future development and regulatory modifications.

5.3.6.2 Potential points of discordance between the practical application of Al-Murabaha

There are a number of potential areas of divergence between the actual implementation of Al-Murabaha and its underlying ethical and economic principles. These discrepancies can stem from various factors, including:

- Complexity of Al-Murabaha transactions: Al-Murabaha transactions can be intricate and may be employed in ways that conflict with Sharia principles. For instance, some Al-Murabaha transactions may involve excessive markups or be utilized to finance activities deemed illicit (haram).

- Lack of standardized practices for Al-Murabaha transactions: The absence of a single standard for Al-Murabaha transactions can lead to inconsistent practices. This can hinder efforts to ensure that Al-Murabaha transactions are always conducted in accordance with Shariah principles.

- Opacity of some Al-Murabaha transactions: Certain Al-Murabaha transactions may be opaque, impeding customers' comprehension of the true financing costs. This can result in unfair treatment of customers and erode the ethical foundations of Islamic finance."

5.3.6.2.1 Examples of potential points of discordance:

1. Unreasonably High Markups:

- Al-Murabaha transactions should not involve excessive markups, as this can lead to unfair profits and disadvantages customers.

- The lack of a clear definition for "unreasonably high markups" can result in inconsistent practices.

2. Engaging in Speculative Activities:

- Al-Murabaha transactions should not be used for speculation, as this can be considered haram (prohibited) under Sharia principles.

- There is a risk that Al-Murabaha transactions may be used for speculative purposes, particularly in commodity financing.

3. Indirect Facilitation of Haram Activities:

- Al-Murabaha transactions should not be used to indirectly finance activities deemed haram, such as alcohol or gambling.

- There is a risk that Al-Murabaha transactions may be indirectly used to support businesses engaged in haram activities.

5.3.6.2.2 Addressing Potential Points of Discordance

1. Enhanced Transparency:

- Greater transparency in Al-Murabaha transactions is crucial to mitigate the risk of deviating from Islamic principles.

- Islamic banks should be required to disclose more information about their Al-Murabaha transactions.

- Standardized practices for Al-Murabaha transactions should be developed to ensure consistent implementation.

2. Improved Regulatory Oversight:

- Regulatory bodies should play a more active role in overseeing the Al-Murabaha industry.

- Clear regulations for Al-Murabaha transactions should be developed to provide guidance to Islamic banks.

- Regular audits of Islamic banks should be conducted to ensure compliance with Sharia principles.

3. Strengthened Sharia Supervisory Boards:

- Sharia supervisory boards play a critical role in ensuring that Islamic banks adhere to Sharia principles.

- These boards should be independent and have the authority to review and reject Al-Murabaha transactions that conflict with Sharia principles.

By implementing these measures, the potential for discordance between the practical application of Al-Murabaha and its ethical and economic underpinnings can be minimized, ensuring that this financing method remains aligned with Islamic principles

5.3.6.2 Current trends in Islamic Banking

The UAE's Islamic banking sector is continually evolving, adapting to changing market conditions and customer preferences. Here are some of the most notable trends in the industry:

1. Tech-driven solutions: Islamic banks in the United Arab Emirates are embracing financial technology (fintech) to enhance the customer experience and optimize operational processes. This includes web and mobile banking platforms, as well as account management tools.

2. Emphasis on sustainability and ethical practices: The Islamic banking sector in the UAE is placing greater importance on sustainable and ethical finance practices. Aligning with global sustainability goals, several institutions are incorporating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations into their investment strategies.

3. Global expansion: Islamic banks headquartered in the UAE are gradually expanding their international presence. The rising demand for Islamic financial services is driving their focus on foreign markets, particularly regions with substantial Muslim populations.

4. Diversified product offerings: To attract a wider range of customers, Islamic banks are increasingly developing non-traditional products. Examples

include Islamic credit cards, digital wallets, and cross-border financial investments.

5. Strategic partnerships and collaborations: To foster innovation and broaden their scope, Islamic banks in the UAE are collaborating with fintech companies, non-banking financial institutions, and international organizations.

6. Regulatory advancements: The UAE Central Bank is continuously striving to enhance its regulatory framework to maintain the competitiveness and security of the Islamic banking sector.

The UAE's dedication to innovation, ethical finance, and global growth has positioned the country's Islamic banking sector for future expansion and influence. As global demand for Islamic financing increases, the UAE is poised to become a leading hub for Islamic banking.

6. Conclusion

The Islamic banking sector in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) has witnessed remarkable growth in recent years, establishing itself as a prominent force in the global Islamic finance landscape. This advancement can be partly attributed to the UAE's robust regulatory framework, which fosters a stable and supportive environment for Islamic banking institutions. Moreover, the UAE's unwavering commitment to Sharia-compliant financial services has attracted a growing clientele and investor base.

Al-Murabaha, a prevalent form of Islamic financing, is widely utilized in the UAE. This financing mechanism is characterized by its transparency and fixed-cost structure, making it suitable for financing a diverse range of assets. Additionally, Al-Murabaha embodies a risk-sharing arrangement, where the bank assumes a portion of the risk should the customer default on the loan.

Despite its advantages, Al-Murabaha presents certain potential drawbacks. For instance, Al-Murabaha transactions may incur higher costs compared to traditional bank transactions, and there exists a risk of fraudulent practices.

Overall, Al-Murabaha stands as a viable and effective financing option that aligns with Islamic principles, enabling the financing of a variety of assets. However, it is crucial to carefully consider the potential drawbacks of this financing method before making a decision regarding its utilization.

To further enhance the future of Islamic banking in the UAE, the following recommendations are proposed:

Continuous development of Sharia-compliant financial products and services

Enhanced awareness and education initiatives regarding Islamic banking

Further strengthening of the regulatory framework for Islamic banking

Unwavering commitment to innovation within the Islamic banking sector

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